

MAGNETIC REFRIGERATION TECHNOLOGY AND APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Up to this time, conventional vapor compression refrigeration systems have been widely used for cooling applications. Refrigerants that contain chlorofluorocarbon and hydrochlorofluorocarbon used in these systems damage the ozone layer. Vapor compression refrigeration systems have both direct and indirect effects on global warming in two ways. Leakage of refrigerant from the system components or it is being spread to the outside during service can be considered as a direct effect. The indirect effect is using a carbon-emitting power plant for the generation of electrical energy used by the refrigeration system. Besides, indirect effects are directly related to the cooling performance coefficient of the system. Nowadays, as system efficiency and environmental impacts are taken into consideration, alternative methods are being searched for refrigeration applications instead of vapor compression refrigeration systems. Researches on magnetocaloric materials and the development of magnetic refrigeration technologies provide an alternative to the conventional vapor-compression refrigeration cycle. Magnetic refrigeration is based on the principle that a ferromagnetic or paramagnetic material exhibits a magnetocaloric effect and this effect allows heat exchange from the environment using a heat transfer fluid in the heat exchanger. These systems have no negative effects on the environment in terms of global warming and the ozone layer. On the other hand, since there are no compression and throttling processes in magnetic refrigeration systems, they are theoretically more efficient than vapor compression systems. Besides, moving parts are reduced in the system, and noise generated during compressor operation is eliminated in magnetic refrigeration. In this study, magnetic refrigeration technology was compared to conventional vapor compression systems in terms of working principle, energy efficiency, cooling performance, and environmental effect. Besides, its application fields were investigated. Thermodynamic cycles that can be used in magnetic refrigeration systems were also examined.

Keywords: Energy efficiency, magnetic refrigeration, magnetocaloric effect.

AMR Active magnetic regenerator
CFC Chlorofluorocarbon
COP Coefficient of performance
Gd Gadolinium
H Magnetic field
HCFC Hydrochlorofluorocarbon
s Entropy
T Temperature (°C)
T Tesla

1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing population and developing technology require more energy, which necessitates new technological methods for energy supply and makes efficient use of energy essential. The main purpose of new methods is energy production and operation costs, environmentally friendly, sensitive to social values, and effective. The issues on the world energy agenda can be listed as follows; efficient use of energy, effective energy

management, alternative fuel options and applicability, renewable energy sources, and environmental problems caused by energy use [1,2].

Nowadays, although conventional vapor compression refrigeration technology is widely used in many places from vehicles to industrial plants, various limitations in the system result in low efficiency. Also, chlorofluorocarbon and the hydrochlorofluorocarbon-containing refrigerant used in these systems damage the ozone layer and affect global warming. Vapor compression refrigeration systems have direct and indirect effects on global warming in two ways. Leakage of the refrigerant from the system components or it is being spread to the outside during service can be considered as a direct effect. The indirect effect is the use of a carbon-emitting powerplant for the generation of electrical energy used by the cooling system compressor. The substantial disadvantage of the vapor compression refrigeration system is that it requires a compressor to compress a large amount of refrigerant vapor which requires a great deal of power to operate. Additionally, environmental factors limit the lowest temperature of the refrigeration cycle and therefore have lower COP than the Carnot cycle [3,4].

Considering the system efficiency and environmental impacts, alternative methods for refrigeration applications are being used instead of vapor compression refrigeration systems. Research on magnetocaloric materials and the development of magnetic refrigeration technologies provide an alternative to the conventional vapor compression refrigeration systems. Magnetic refrigeration is based on the principle that a ferromagnetic or paramagnetic material exhibits a magnetocaloric effect and this effect allows heat exchange from the environment using a heat transfer fluid in the heat exchanger. These systems have no adverse effects on the environment in terms of global warming and the ozone layer. On the other hand, since there are no compression and throttling processes in magnetic refrigeration systems, they are theoretically more efficient than vapor compression systems. Also, moving parts are reduced in the system, and noise generated during compressor operation is eliminated in magnetic refrigeration [5-7].

In this study, the magnetocaloric effect which is the basic principle of magnetic refrigeration technology is explained and the working principle of the magnetic refrigeration system is mentioned, magnetic refrigeration technology was compared to conventional vapor compression systems in terms of working principle, energy efficiency, cooling performance and environmental effect and its application fields were investigated.

2. PRINCIPLES OF MAGNETIC REFRIGERATION SYSTEM

The working principle of magnetic refrigerators is based on the magnetocaloric effect, perceived as an adiabatic temperature change or isothermal entropy change. The magnetocaloric effect was discovered by Emil Warburg in 1881 with its effect on iron. Debye and Giauque also independently defined the magnetocaloric effect. Besides, these scientists have guided practical use of the magnetocaloric effect, such as removal of adiabatic demagnetization and reaching lower temperatures than liquid helium, the lowest experimental temperature that can be obtained [8,9].

To define the magnetocaloric effect, thermodynamic relations are used to associate the magnetic variables with magnetization and magnetic field with entropy and temperature. All materials have magnetocaloric effects, but the intensity of this effect depends on the properties of the material. The physical origin of the magnetocaloric effect is that the applied magnetic field causes a change in the entropy of the material [10].

As shown in Figure 1, the isothermal magnetization of a paramagnet or ferromagnet is similar to the isothermal compression of a gas. The magnetic field is applied and entropy is reduced. The pressure is applied and entropy is reduced. Adiabatic demagnetization is similar to the adiabatic expansion of a gas temperature decreases when the pressure decreases in constant entropy. The total entropy remains constant when the magnetic field acting on the material is removed and the temperature decreases due to the increase in magnetic entropy [11].

Figure 1. The isothermal process causing entropy change in magnetocaloric effect and adiabatic process with temperature change observed.

One of the most essential examples in which the magnetocaloric effect can be observed is the chemical element gadolinium and some alloys. Gadolinium and its alloys have gained an important place in magnetic cooling systems thanks to their unique magnetic properties. Furthermore, these magnetocaloric materials are the best available materials for magnetic refrigeration close to room temperature since they are subject to second-order phase transitions. Curie temperature is the critical temperature at which a ferromagnetic material loses its permanent magnetism and becomes paramagnetic. Gadolinium, a typical magnetocaloric material, can exhibit a maximum adiabatic temperature change of 2.5 °C at Curie temperature and 1 Tesla magnetic field strength. As shown in Figure 2, this value increase in proportion to the magnetic field strength [12].

Figure 2. Gadolinium adiabatic temperature change.

In the conventional vapor compression cycle, the refrigerant fluid is compressed its temperature is increased, then the compressed gas gives heat to the environment through a condenser, the fluid decreases in temperature, the expanded gas draws heat from the environment to be cooled, and the cycle starts again.

Figure 3. Similarities between the vapor compression system and the magnetic refrigeration systems.

Magnetic refrigeration is based on the principle that a ferromagnetic or paramagnetic material exhibits a magnetocaloric effect, and this effect allows heat exchange from the environment using a heat transfer fluid in the heat exchanger. In the magnetic refrigeration cycle, the heat is increased by exposing the magnetocaloric material to the magnetic field. The magnetized magnetocaloric material gives heat to the environment. The material is demagnetized, and its temperature is lowered, the fluid draws heat from the environment to be cooled, and the cycle begins again. To carry heat transfer on magnetocaloric material under the influence of the magnetic field, water, and ethyl alcohol derivative fluids are used as a refrigerant in the system. The fact that the magnetocaloric material enters and exits the magnetic field along with gradually flowing liquid flow replaces the function of the compressor in a conventional vapor cycle. Figure 3 shows the similarities between the vapor compression system and the magnetic refrigeration systems [13].

Since the 1930s, magnetic cooling has been used as a laboratory technique to reach shallow temperatures. However, working close to room temperature has recently been possible with rare earth metals and transition metal-based refrigerants and permanent high field and superconducting magnets. Although gadolinium is one of the best magnetocaloric materials available, the temperature differences that can be achieved with the magnetocaloric effect are low. For this reason, it is very complicated to describe the use of the magnetocaloric effect in many cooling applications. This technical obstacle was overcome by integrating the active magnetic regenerator into the system. Regeneration in magnetic refrigeration systems ensures that the heat discharged by the system is taken back at any step of the cycle and sent back to the system in another step in the same cycle. Thus, the capacity used for cooling the network load can be used effectively to increase the actual change of entropy and the obtained temperature difference [14].

The sample active magnetic regenerative cycle is operated as shown in Figure 4 for a steady-state condition. In the first stage (a), the initial temperature profile (dashed line) is for the zero magnetic fields. When the magnetic field is applied, each particle in the bed heats up with a magnetocaloric effect (solid line). The amount that each particle warms up is equal to the adiabatic temperature change upon magnetization at the initial temperature of the particle. This value decreases with the effect of the heat capacity of the liquid in the pores between the particles. In the next stage (b), the cold fluid flows from the cold end in the bed to the hot end. The bed is cooled by the fluid, and the fluid reaches a value close to the bed temperature at the hot end, reducing the temperature profile across the bed. Since the temperature reached by the fluid is above the ambient temperature, heat is removed from the environment with the hot end heat exchanger. Then (c) the fluid flow is stopped, and the bed is cooled by removing the magnetic field effect. The cycle continues by forcing the fluid to flow from the hot end of the bed to the cold end. The fluid is lowered below the ambient temperature to be cooled by the bed (d). The cold fluid draws heat from the medium to be cooled by the cold end heat exchanger and the cycle is completed [15,16].

Figure 4. Active magnetic regenerator cycle.

3. THERMODYNAMICS OF MAGNETIC REFRIGERATION SYSTEMS

Carnot, Ericsson, and Brayton cycles are used for thermodynamically magnetic refrigeration systems. However, the most suitable cycles for room temperature applications are the Ericsson and Brayton cycles, where high cooling efficiency in magnetic materials can be achieved [17].

Figure 5. Carnot cycle T-s diagram for magnetic refrigeration.

As seen in Figure 5, the Carnot cycle process (1-2) is the adiabatic magnetization step. While the magnetization process (2-3) continues increasingly, it becomes isothermal magnetization. The heat generated during this process is removed from the system. The next step (3-4) is adiabatic demagnetization. The cycle is completed when the system combines with the heat source during the adiabatic demagnetization phase (4-1). It appears that the Carnot cycle can only be operated if the magnetocaloric material is moved and at least four different magnetic fields are created. In the process (1-2) the magnetic field strength should be changed quickly to prevent heat losses. For isothermal magnetization conditions to occur (2-3) magnetic field change and heat removal from the system must be simultaneous. The area between (1-2-3-4) represents the work required, and the area (1-4-a-b) is related to thermal cooling energy [18].

Figure 6. Ericsson cycle T-s diagram for magnetic refrigeration.

The magnetic refrigerator, where the Ericsson cycle is preferred, operates within two iso-therms and two iso-magnetic fields, as can be shown in Figure 6. This process requires heat regeneration. During the iso-magnetic field process (1-2), heat is absorbed from the opposite side (3-4) using a regenerator. For this reason, in ideal regeneration, the area (2-1-b-d), representing thermal energy absorption from the magnetocaloric material has to correspond to (3-4-a-c), representing the heat extraction of the refrigerant material. Regeneration can only be done if there is a temperature difference. The efficiency of the Ericsson cycle decreases due to the irreversible heat transfer. A simultaneous alteration of the magnetic field and heat absorption or rejection leads to the isothermal processes (2-3), and (4-1). The area (1-2-3-4) represents the work required for the Ericsson cycle and the area (1-4-a-b) is identical to the cooling energy [19].

Figure 7. Brayton cycle T-s diagram for magnetic refrigeration.

Figure 7 shows the Brayton cycle, one of the most fundamental cycles of magnetic refrigeration. The magnetic refrigerator, where the Brayton cycle is preferred, operates between two iso-fields (constant magnetic fields) and

two isentropic curves (constant total specific entropy). Total entropy remains constant by processing the magnetocaloric material through the transition to a magnetic field (1-2). In this case, adiabatic magnetization increases the temperature of the magnetocaloric material. The heat of the material is rejected at this high temperature (2-3). In the adiabatic demagnetization process (3-4), the temperature of the material decreases. At the last stage (4-1), an external device is cooled by absorbing heat in the heat source [19].

4. RESULTS

Today, it is aimed to develop new technologies that use energy efficiently, are sensitive to social values, and are environmentally friendly due to the limited energy resources, increasing energy consumption and demand, and global problems such as global warming. Conventional vapor compression refrigeration systems have been widely used in many fields from industrial facilities to the automotive industry for many years. Research on magnetocaloric materials and the development of magnetic refrigeration technologies provide an alternative to the conventional vapor compression refrigeration systems.

Magnetic refrigeration is a green and environmentally friendly technology considering the desired properties on the minimum effect on global warming. Due to the unavoidable installation leaks, a certain amount of CFC or HCFC gases are mixed directly into the atmosphere every year from the vapor compression refrigeration systems. Since the refrigerants used in magnetic refrigeration are water and ethyl alcohol derivatives which are environmentally friendly liquids, they do not pose an environmental hazard in case of mixing into the atmosphere due to leaks. Magnetic refrigeration technology has the potential to reduce operating and maintenance costs compared to the conventional vapor compression method. Since there is no compressor in magnetic refrigeration systems, the moving parts are reduced and the noise generated during operation is eliminated. It can replace the conventional method by eliminating the high initial investment cost of the compressor and reducing the cost of electrical energy required to operate the system. On the other hand, since there are no compression and throttling processes, they theoretically more efficient than vapor compression refrigeration. Low refrigerant pressure increases the usability of the system in the automotive industry and local air conditioning.

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